

Description of Takotsubo syndrome in a cohort undergoing coronary arteriography

Descripción del síndrome de Takotsubo en una cohorte sometida a arteriografía coronaria

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Agradecimientos Ninguno

Financiamiento El proceso de investigación y publicación fue financiado por la universidad a la que están afiliados los autores. Universidad de La Sabana, Code MEDEsp-74-2023

Conflicto de intereses Los autores declaran no tener conflicto de intereses.

Received: 10/20/2022 Accepted: 01/19/2023 Published: 02/25/2023 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7779126>

Abstract

Background: Takotsubo syndrome (TS) is characterized by a self-resolving state of acute left ventricular failure associated with physical and/or emotional factors. The incidence of TS in patients undergoing coronary arteriography is variable, and the disease frequency is not known in our region.

Objective: Describe the demographic, clinical, and diagnostic characteristics of a cohort of patients with and without a diagnosis of TS who underwent coronary catheterization.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study was conducted in a population older than 18 years of age, regardless of gender, with clinical symptoms of dyspnea and chest pain undergoing coronary arteriography. The diagnostic criteria proposed by the Mayo Clinic were used, where there must be one confirmatory and three exclusion criteria for the diagnosis.

Results: A total of 311 patients were included, of which 1.9% (6/311) had a diagnosis of TS and 56.6% (176/311) were men. The triggering factors related to the onset of symptoms that led to the diagnostic suspicion of TS were unknown in 77.8% (242/311). Chest pain occurred in 83.9% of the population.

Conclusion: The incidence of TS in patients undergoing coronary catheterization is low, whose main trigger was of unknown origin. Multicenter studies are required for further extrapolation of results.

Keywords: Takotsubo syndrome; Percutaneous Coronary Intervention; Acute Coronary Syndrome; Incidence.

Resumen

Introducción: El síndrome de Takotsubo (ST) se caracteriza por un estado de insuficiencia ventricular izquierda aguda autorresolutiva asociada a factores físicos y/o emocionales. La incidencia de ST en pacientes llevados a arteriografía coronaria es variable, sin conocerse en nuestra región la frecuencia de la enfermedad.

Objetivo: Describir las características demográficas, clínicas y diagnósticas de una cohorte de pacientes con y sin diagnóstico de ST sometidos a cateterismo coronario.

Métodos Se realizó un estudio de cohorte retrospectivo en población mayor de 18 años de edad, independiente del género, con sintomatología clínica de disnea y dolor torácico sometidos a arteriografía coronaria. Se utilizaron los criterios diagnósticos propuestos por la Mayo Clinic en donde debe haber uno confirmatorio y tres de exclusión para el diagnóstico.

Resultados: Se incluyeron un total de 311 pacientes de los cuales el 1,9% (6/311) presentó diagnóstico de ST y el 56,6% (176/311) eran hombres. Los factores desencadenantes relacionados con el inicio de sintomatología que llevó a la sospecha diagnóstica de ST fueron desconocidos en el 77,8% (242/311). El dolor torácico se presentó en el 83,9% de la población.

Conclusión: La incidencia del ST en pacientes llevados a cateterismo coronario es baja, cuyo mayor desencadenante fue de origen desconocido. Se requieren estudios multicéntricos para una mayor extrapolación de resultados.

Palabras clave: Síndrome Takotsubo; Intervención Coronaria Percutánea; Síndrome Coronario Agudo; Incidencia.

Takotsubo syndrome (TS) is a condition characterized by a state of self-resolving acute left ventricular failure associated in up to 70% to physical and/or emotional factors¹. The prevalence of the disease goes from 1 to 2.5%, even reaching values of 10% in the female population in the postmenopausal stage, while the recurrence rate is 1.8% for each patient annually^{1,2}. Approximately 50% of patients diagnosed with TS suffer from acute or chronic neurological and psychiatric diseases^{3,4}.

In countries such as Switzerland, the United States, and Japan, it has been reported that TS has a prevalence ranging between 1.7% and 2.3% in subjects presenting symptoms of acute coronary syndrome (ACS)⁵⁻⁷. Deshmukh et al.⁸, described a population of 6,837 patients in the United States with a diagnosis of TS in which 90% were at least 50 years or older at the time of diagnosis, 90.4% were women, and the most frequent comorbidities were hyperlipidemia, anxiety, and smoking. On the contrary, in a cohort of 18 patients from Colombia, it was observed that the average age was 59.5 years, 66.7% were women, and the most frequent comorbidities were arterial hypertension, depression, and smoking⁹.

The incidence of TS in patients undergoing coronary angiography is variable, with data reported from 1 to 10% in hospitalized patients, without knowing its incidence in our region⁹⁻¹¹. Therefore, knowing the incidence of patients diagnosed with TS in our population can improve the current knowledge about this syndrome and eventually generate management and follow-up strategies in this population, however, few studies describe the characteristics of this condition in detail. This research aims to describe the demographic, clinical, and diagnostic characteristics of a cohort of patients with and without a diagnosis of TS who underwent coronary catheterization.

A retrospective cohort study was carried out in a population that underwent coronary arteriography (CA) in a tertiary-level hospital in Bogotá, Colombia, between 2018 and 2019.

Eligibility criteria

Patients over 18 years of age, regardless of gender, with clinical symptoms of dyspnea and chest pain were included. Patients with a diagnosis of acute myocardial infarction confirmed by CA and myocarditis diagnosed by electrocardiographic and echocardiographic findings were excluded.

The diagnostic criteria proposed by the Mayo Clinic were applied¹², where there must be at least one confirmatory criteria and three exclusion criteria for diagnosis. First, the patient must present hypokinesia, akinesia, or dyskinesia in the middle segments of the left ventricle with or without apical involvement, with motility disorders that go beyond an epicardial level, and a stressor event or stimulus; second, the absence of obstructive coronary disease or angiographic evidence of plaque rupture; third, new and recent electrocardiographic abnormalities (st elevation or T wave inversion), or moderate elevation of troponins; and finally, no diagnosis of pheochromocytoma or myocarditis. It should be clarified that regarding some of these criteria, there are circumstances in which there is no clear stressor or in which the motility disorders are present only at the coronary level and even then, a diagnosis of TS can be made.

Variables

The variables of age, gender, pathological history, TS episode triggers, signs, and symptoms upon admission to the medical center were the ones evaluated. Biomarkers of myocardial injury, electrocardiogram, CA, and left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) measured with transthoracic echocardiography were also evaluated.

Sample

All study subjects who met the selection criteria were entered into the cohort, data were collected by trained personnel reviewing clinical records, arteriography, and echocardiographic reports of the acute event, and data review were performed by two researchers to avoid possible transcription errors.

Statistical analysis

Continuous variables were synthesized using mean and standard deviation (SD) if they had a normal distribution, and in median interquartile range if the distribution was not normal. The discrete variables were synthesized in proportions and frequencies. An exploratory bivariate analysis was performed in relation to the presence or absence of employing chi-square tests for the qualitative variables, the quantitative variables were analyzed using the Student's T or Mann Whitney U test depending on their distribution.

Statistical analysis was performed using the licensed SPSS version 25 program.

Ethical considerations

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the Hospital Universitario de La Samaritana, considering it a risk-free investigation according to resolution 8430 of 1993, therefore it was not necessary to obtain informed consent, this investigation respects the protection of personal data according to the habeas data law 1266 of 2008.

Results

A total of 311 patients were included, of whom 1.9% (6/311) presented a diagnosis of TS, the average age was 60.7 years (SD: 13.5) and 56.6% (176/ 311) were men. 62.7% (195/311) of the patients had a history of systemic arterial hypertension, 42.8% (133/311) hypercholesterolemia, and 25.7% (80/311) ischemic heart disease. The demographic characteristics are shown in Table 1.

Tabla 1. Características demográficas de la población

Variables	Población total n=311
Edad años x(de)	60,7 (13,5)
Genero n(%)	
Masculino	176 (56,6)
Femenino	135 (43,4)
Antecedentes patológicos n(%)	
Hipertensión arterial sistémica	195 (62,7)
Diabetes mellitus	63 (20,3)
Tabaquismo	69 (22,2)
Hipercolesterolemia	133 (42,8)
Enfermedad coronaria	25 (8,0)
Obesidad	41 (13,2)
Desorden neurológico	28 (9,0)
Desorden psiquiátrico	9 (2,9)
Cardiopatía isquémica	80 (25,7)
Enfermedad renal crónica	19 (6,1)

The triggering factors related to the onset of symptoms that led to the suspected diagnosis of TS were unknown in the 77.8% (242/311) and physical in the 17.7% (55/311) Table 2. Chest pain was presented in 83.9% of the population. Qualitative troponin c was positive in 63.3% (197/311), and 15.8% (49/311) of the patients presented electrocardiographic signs of ST-segment depression.

The CA was positive for coronary disease in 58.5% (182/311) of the study population Table 3. The mean LVEF was 53.0% (SD: 12.7) and 52.4% (163/311) of patients had a baseline echocardiographic abnormality in motility.

Tabla 2. Variables clínicas y exámenes de laboratorio	
Variables	Población total n=311
Desencadenante del episodio n(%)	
Físico	55 (17,7)
Emocional	12 (3,9)
Físico/Emocional	2 (0,6)
Desconocido	242 (77,8)
Síntomas y signos al ingreso n(%)	
Disnea	148 (47,6)
Dolor torácico	261 (83,9)
Biomarcador positivo n(%)	
Troponina c	197 (63,3)
Péptido natriurético cerebral	1 (0,3)
Electrocardiograma n(%)	
Elevación segmento ST	25 (8,0)
Depresión segmento ST	49 (15,8)
Inversión de la onda T	13 (4,2)
Intervalo QT prolongado	12 (3,9)

Tabla 3. Hallazgos en arteriografía coronaria y ecocardiograma

Variables	Población total n=311
Enfermedad coronaria en arteriografía n(%)	182 (58,5)
Fracción de eyección del VI x(de)	53,0 (12,7)
Alteración de la motilidad n(%)	
Basal	163 (52,4)
Medial	108 (34,79)
Apical	121 (38,9)
Miocarditis	2 (0,6)

Notas: VI, ventrículo izquierdo.

Discussion

This study described the frequency and clinical characteristics of TS in a population taken to CA, evidencing a prevalence similar to that reported in the medical literature, even in a population not subjected to cardiac catheterization^{2,4,6,10}. The male gender predominated in more than half of the population, the main triggering factor of the episode probably compatible with TS was unknown, and the most common prodromal symptom was chest pain. The echocardiogram findings revealed a motility disorder mainly at baseline, with no changes consistent with reduced LVEF. The pathological antecedents most frequently presented were systemic arterial hypertension, hypercholesterolemia and ischemic heart disease. Troponin C was elevated in more than half of the population, and less than 10% of the population had ST-segment elevation or prolonged QT interval.

Currently, an incidence of TS is described that can vary between age groups and/or geographical areas, in women living in Japan, a rate of up to 10% of the hospitalized population is estimated^{1,4,6,7}. In countries such as Switzerland decreases to 7% and in Western countries in North and South America with a frequency of 1.7 to 2.2%, these last data are similar to those reported in our study cohort^{1,4,7,10,13}. The clinical manifestations of TS can present as an ACS mimic given by symptoms such as chest pain and/or dyspnea, in addition to changes in the electrocardiogram and elevation of biomarkers compatible with myocardial ischemia³, making it essential to rule out the presence of acute coronary artery disease by CA^{3,4}. Typical echocardiographic findings of the disease represent contractile dysfunction of the apical, basal, or medial segments, secondary apical bulging, and a reduction in LVEF^{3,4,7}.

The perception of stress or emotional factors together with the activation of the sympathetic autonomic system generates an increase of up to three times in catecholamines and an acute deregulation of myocardial sympathetic physiology and apical, medial and/or basal hypokinesia¹⁴, these last given by a interstitial mononuclear inflammatory response, persistent edema 3 to 4 months after the acute episode, contraction band necrosis, and catecholamine overstimulation of the G protein-mediated β 1AR and β 2AR signaling pathways^{15,16}. On the other hand, acute atrioventricular stretching and inflammation as a direct consequence of exposure to adrenaline and/or noradrenaline can trigger episodes of QT interval prolongation and T wave inversion (Wellen's sign) 3 to 4 days after the clinical picture¹⁷. It is striking that in our cohort a low frequency of prolonged QT interval was reported and the most common triggering factor was not identified as physical or emotional, this last situation is being reported more frequently in the medical literature

Doyen et al.¹⁸, described the clinical characteristics in a cohort of 280 patients hospitalized in the intensive care unit, of whom 13 had a diagnosis of TS, 15 with ACS, and 252 healthy patients. An incidence of TS of 4.6% was found using the Mayo Clinic criteria, reaching 7.6% in the female gender. In patients with TS, the average LVEF was 29% (IQR: 20-37%), left ventricular dysfunction occurred in the 92.3% (12/13), 46.3% (2/13) developed cardiac arrhythmias and compromise in myocardial motility was affected mainly at the apical and medial level. On the contrary, in our cohort there was no evidence of a drastic decrease in LVEF and the basal involvement predominated over the apical one, these differences were probably due to severity, a guided therapeutic approach in the intensive care unit, and an average age 4 years older than the patients presented by Doyen.

TS is an acute heart failure that predominantly affects postmenopausal women after emotional or physical stress with a worse prognosis and complications, reporting less hemodynamic compromise and regional motion abnormalities of the apical myocardial wall in women on fertile age. Gómez et al.,¹⁹ described a series of 12 women who attended

the cardiac catheterization unit, with an average age of 61.4 years (SD: 12.05) and emotional triggers, only in two cases was it not possible to establish the origin. Stronger cardiovascular antecedents were previous ACS and systemic arterial hypertension, hypothyroidism was the most frequent non-cardiological antecedent. Contrary to what has been described in the medical literature, in our cohort there was no predominance of affectation in the female gender probably because the subjects who underwent catheterization had a cardiovascular and/or metabolic history that makes them more likely to present with an acute myocardial infarction.

Auger et al.²⁰, in a retrospective cohort study, determined the mortality and morbidity of 174 patients diagnosed with TS during 15 years of follow-up, compared with 1,736 patients diagnosed with ACS and 1,740 healthy patients. TS was shown to have a similar in-hospital mortality risk to ACS patients (HR: 1.06; 95% CI: 0.81-1.38), and a higher risk of cardiovascular rehospitalization (HR: 2, 71, 95% CI: 2.24-3.28) compared to the control group. The authors mention a higher risk of in-hospital cardiovascular morbidity and mortality compared to healthy controls, including diseases such as ischemic heart disease, hypertension, atherosclerosis, and other vascular and arterial diseases. Although we did not evaluate the outcomes described by Auger, we believe that the performance of CA and the high frequency of arterial hypertension and hypercholesterolemia could have increased the rate of hospitalizations and complications during our study.

Limitations

Among the main limitations, it stands out that it was a single-center study that limits the extrapolation of results, however, the sample size achieved gives a clear idea of this pathology in patients taken to CA. Secondly, there is the type of study that is a retrospective cohort, which, by requiring information from medical records, is subject to the quality of the records. Multicenter studies are required for further extrapolation of results.

Conclusions

The incidence of TS in patients taken to CA is low, whose main trigger was of unknown origin.

References

1. Y-Hassan S, Tornvall P. Epidemiology, pathogenesis, and management of takotsubo syndrome. *Clin Auton Res*. 2018; 28(1):53-65.
2. Amin HZ, Amin LZ, Pradipta A. Takotsubo Cardiomyopathy: A Brief Review. *J Med Life*. 2020; 13(1):3-7.
3. Gupta, S., & Gupta, M. M. (2018). Takotsubo syndrome. *Indian heart journal*, 70(1),165–174.
4. Templin C, Napp LC, Ghadri JR. Takotsubo syndrome: underdiagnosed, underestimated, but understood? *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2016; 67(16):1937–1940
5. Y-Hassan S. Takotsubo syndrome and malignancy: Prevalence and mortality. *Int J Cardiol*. 2020; 309:23-24.
6. Aizawa K, Suzuki T. Takotsubo cardiomyopathy: Japanese perspective. *Heart Fail Clin*. 2013; 9(2):243-7, x.
7. Akashi YJ, Nef HM, Lyon AR. Epidemiology and pathophysiology of Takotsubo syndrome. *Nat Rev Cardiol*. 2015; 12(7):387-97.
8. Deshmukh A, Kumar G, Pant S, Rihal C, Murugiah K, Mehta JL. Prevalence of Takotsubo cardiomyopathy in the United States. *Am Heart J*. 2012;164(1):66-71.e1.
9. Naranjo Restrepo S, Múnera Echeverri AG, Gaviria Aguilar MC, Gutiérrez Prieto D, Vásquez Trespalacios EM, Duque Ramírez M. Características clínicas, demográficas y epidemiológicas de una cohorte de pacientes con síndrome de Takotsubo entre 2011 y 2016 en Medellín, Colombia. *Rev médicas UIS*. 2021;34(1).
10. Gómez AR, Herrera S, Ochoa J, Velásquez JG. Miocardiopatía por estrés: serie de casos. *Rev colomb cardiol*. 2015; 22(2):97–101.
11. Lyon AR, Bossone E, Schneider B, Sechtem U, Citro R, Underwood SR, et al. Current state of knowledge on Takotsubo syndrome: a Position Statement from the Taskforce on Takotsubo Syndrome of the Heart Failure Association of the European Society of Cardiology. *Eur J Heart Fail*. 2016; 18(1):8-27.
12. Scantlebury DC, Prasad A. Diagnosis of takotsubo cardiomyopathy – Mayo Clinic criteria –. *Circulation Journal*. 2014; 78(9):2129-2139.
13. Cammann VL, Würdinger M, Ghadri JR, Templin C. Takotsubo Syndrome: Uncovering Myths and Misconceptions. *Curr Atheroscler Rep*. 2021; 23(9):53.
14. Lyon AR, Citro R, Schneider B, Morel O, Ghadri JR, Templin C, Omerovic E. Pathophysiology of Takotsubo Syndrome: JACC State-of-the-Art Review. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2021; 77(7):902-921.
15. Scally C, Abbas H, Ahearn T, Srinivasan J, Mezincescu A, Rudd A, Spath N, Yucel-Finn A, Yucel R, Oldroyd K, Dospinescu C, Horgan G, Broadhurst P, Henning A, Newby DE, Semple S, Wilson HM, Dawson DK. Myocardial and Systemic Inflammation in Acute Stress-Induced (Takotsubo) Cardiomyopathy. *Circulation*. 2019; 139(13):1581-1592.
16. Matta A, Delmas C, Campelo-Parada F, Lhermusier T, Bouisset F, Elbaz M, Nader V, Blanco S, Roncalli J, Carrié D. Takotsubo cardiomyopathy. *Rev Cardiovasc Med*. 2022 Jan 20; 23(1):38.
17. Jesel L, Berthon C, Messas N, Lim HS, Girardey M, Marzak H, Marchandot B, Trinh A, Ohlmann P, Morel O. Atrial arrhythmias in Takotsubo cardiomyopathy: incidence, predictive factors, and prognosis. *Europace*. 2019; 21(2):298-305.
18. Doyen D, Moschietto S, Squara F, Mocerì P, Hyvernat H, Ferrari E, Dellamonica J, Bernardin G. Incidence, clinical features and outcome of Takotsubo syndrome in the intensive care unit. *Arch Cardiovasc Dis*. 2020; 113(3):176-188.
19. Gómez AR, Herrera S, Ochoa J, Velásquez JG. Miocardiopatía por estrés: serie de casos. *Rev colomb cardiol*. 2015;22(2):97–101.
20. Auger N, Paradis G, Healy-Profítos J, He S, Potter BJ. Outcomes of Takotsubo Syndrome at 15 Years: A Matched Cohort Study. *Am J Med*. 2020; 133(5):627-634.e4.